

Thermal Stability of Dioctadecyldimethylammonium Bromide (DOAB) Vesicles in Aqueous Solutions containing Hexadecyltrimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB)

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Manuscript received 15 January 1993

When hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) is added to dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DOAB) vesicles in aqueous solutions, the gel to liquid crystal transition temperature is unaffected in the first scan of a differential scanning microcalorimeter. Subsequent scans are more complicated indicating that monomeric CTAB can penetrate the DOAB vesicles when the latter are in the liquid crystalline form.

In aqueous solution, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) forms micelles¹ when the concentration of CTAB exceeds the critical micellar concentration² (cmc), approx. 8×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ at 298 K. In micelles, the hydrophobic alkyl chains, by coming into close proximity, minimise their contact with the aqueous solution. With increase in concentration, the CTAB micelles aggregate to form clusters of micelles³.

In aqueous solution the amphiphile dioctadecyldimethylammonium bromide (DOAB) forms vesicles^{4,5}. These surfactant assemblies are interesting examples of supramolecular chemistry. Moreover they have a close relationship with biologically important structures formed by phospholipids. In the vesicles formed by DOAB, their structure involves close contact between the alkyl chain, the vesicles presenting the polar head groups, $> N^+Me_2$ and Br^- counter anions to the aqueous solution. At low temperatures the dialkyl chains pack in ordered fashion. But with increase in temperature, the vesicles undergo a gel to liquid crystalline transition at temperature T_m characteristic of the system. This transition is conveniently de-

termined using a differential scanning microcalorimeter³. For DOAB in aqueous solution the recorded scan identifies two extrema attributed to intervesicular and intravesicular processes⁶ respectively. In the latter process, the dependence on temperature of the differential heat capacity δC_p can be analysed⁷ to yield the size of the cooperative unit which corresponds to the number of surfactants monomers (patch number) involved in the melting transition (gel to liquid crystalline states) characterised by T_m together with the enthalpy change per mole of monomer unit, $\Delta_r H^0$. For DOAB we find⁶ that the intervesicular process produces an extremum at 35.9° (Celsius) when [DOAB] equals 3×10^{-3} (mol monomer) dm⁻³. For the intramolecular 'gel to liquid crystalline' transition, T_m equals 44.8°, and the patch number n equals 131 where $\Delta_r H^0$ equals 8.89 kcal (monomer mol⁻¹). In other words, at 44.8° the dialkyl chains within DOAB vesicles move from an ordered gel state to a liquid crystalline state where the chains gain considerable local freedom. The question then emerged as to how T_m and other parameters might change if another hydrophobic cosolute is entrapped within the hydrophobic domains of the vesicles. To this end we examined therefore

the effect on the scans recorded by a differential scanning microcalorimeter of adding CTAB to DOAB(aq). We reasoned that CTAB has a similar polar head group, $-\text{NMe}_3^+\text{Br}^-$ to that in DOAB, namely $>\text{NMe}_2^+\text{Br}^-$ which we anticipated would allow incorporation of the alkyl chains of CTAB into the bilayer structures of DOAB vesicles. These experiments are important in view of the current interest in the interaction of surfactants with biological membranes⁸. We report that T_m shifts to lower temperatures with increase in [CTAB] consistent with a decrease in thermal stability of the gel state. However the behaviour is rather more complicated than this latter statement suggests. In fact the first scan for these mixed systems differs from all subsequent scans suggesting that CTAB monomers readily penetrate DOAB vesicles in the liquid crystalline state.

Results and Discussion

An overview of the results is provided by the data summarised in Fig. 1. The scans reproduced in the Figure are consistently the second scan recorded for each solution (see Experimental section). The trace labelled (a) in Fig. 1 was obtained from

Fig. 1. Dependences on temperature of the differential isobaric heat capacities for DOAB [aq; 2×10^{-3} (monomer mol) dm^{-3}] in the presence of various concentrations of CTAB. In each case the trace records the second scan, that is after the solution had been heated in the calorimeter to 90° and subsequently re-cooled to 15° ; [CTAB]/mol dm^{-3} = (a) 0.0, (b) 5×10^{-4} , (c) 1×10^{-3} , (d) 1.5×10^{-3} , (e) 2.0×10^{-3} , and (f) 2.5×10^{-3} . For clarity the scans have been displaced on the heat capacity axis.

DOAB (aq) vesicles alone and all features have been shown to be reversible in the sense that the DSC trace remained the same during subsequent heat \rightarrow cool \rightarrow heat \rightarrow cycles, showing that the features near 36° and 45° are characteristic equilibrium properties of the system. The remaining plots in Fig. 1 show that added CTAB removes completely the extremum at 36° . Moreover with further increase in [CTAB], the extremum at 45° shifts to lower temperatures. However Fig. 1 hides other complexities.

When the concentration of CTAB is smaller than that comparable to the cmc, the extremum recorded in the first scan is only slightly below T_m , 44.1° recorded in the absence of CTAB. But on subsequent scans the extremum is at 43.1° ; Fig. 2. On the low temperature side of the extrema there is evidence of a significant broadening of the classic bell-shape. In fact as shown in Fig. 3, the envelope is satisfactorily fitted (ORIGIN software) to two contributing bell-shaped dependences; (i) $T_m = 42.3^\circ$, where $\Delta_r H^\circ = 3.7$ kcal (monomer mol) $^{-1}$, and (ii) $T_m = 43.2^\circ$, where $\Delta_r H^\circ = 6.1$ kcal mol $^{-1}$ where the patch number is 114. With increase in [CTAB], the uniqueness of the first scan becomes more apparent. When [CTAB] equals 1.5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} (Fig. 4), the first scan shows a small well-resolved feature on the low temperature (41°) side of the main feature at 43.3° . This pattern is further developed when more CTAB is added to DOAB(aq). In Fig. 5, we present the scans obtained for aqueous solutions containing equal concentrations (2×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) of DOAB and CTAB. The first scan shows two extrema at 40.4 and 43.1° . In subsequent scans the feature at high temperature dominates but now at 41° with the minor feature near 39° .

The first noteworthy common effect of added CTAB is the disappearance of the low temperature extremum which we previously attributed to intervesicular DOAB interaction⁷. We attempted for comparison to monitor the effect of added NaBr but the outcome was unhelpful in that an insoluble precipitate was formed. However, if the assignment of the lower temperature transition to intervesicular

Fig. 2. Dependence on temperature of the differential isobaric heat capacity δC_p for DOAB [2×10^{-3} (monomer mol) dm^{-3}] in aqueous solution containing CTAB (1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}); scans are recorded following cooling in the calorimeter, following preparation at 15° [scan a], following heating to 90° and cooling to 15° [scans (b) and (c)] and following standing for 3 h at 15° [scans (d) and (e)]. For clarity the scans have been displaced on the heat capacity axis.

Fig. 3. Dependence on temperature of molar relaxational heat capacity C_{pm} for DOAB [2×10^{-3} (monomer mol) dm^{-3}] in aqueous solution containing CTAB (1×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}); recorded dependence (—) and calculated dependence (---).

processes is correct, then it appears that CTAB monomers and micelles at comparatively low CTAB concentrations prevent aggregation of DOAB vesicles. Turning to the effect of added CTAB on the processes responsible for the extremum at 45° , it is important to draw into the discussion the cmc of CTAB, particularly in the context of the range of concentra-

Fig. 4. Dependence on temperature of differential heat capacity for DOAB [2×10^{-3} (monomer mol) dm^{-3}] in aqueous solutions containing CTAB (1.5×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}). The first scan is labelled (a) and the remainder of the scans are for solutions prepared using the protocol summarised in the caption to Fig. 2. For clarity the scans have been displaced on the heat capacity axis.

Fig. 5. Dependence on temperature of the differential heat capacity for DOAB [2×10^{-3} (monomer mol) dm^{-3}] in aqueous solution containing CTAB (2×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}); scans were recorded following cooling in the calorimeter to 15° [scan (a)] following heating to 90° and cooling to 15° [scan (b)]. Scans (c), (d) and (e) were recorded following cooling to 15° and holding at 15° for 3 h. Scan (f) was recorded after cooling to and storing at 15° for 11 h. For clarity the scans have been displaced on the heat capacity axis.

tions of added CTAB described in Fig. 1. It is also important to recall from the methods discussed in the Experimental section that CTAB was added to the DOAB(aq) at 15° .

At low concentrations where $[\text{CTAB}] \leq \text{cmc}$,

the CTAB is present as monomers. Nevertheless these surfactant molecules clearly insulate the vesicles from each other thereby removing the extremum at 36° attributed to intervesicular interaction. When more CTAB is added (cf. Fig. 2), some of the CTAB monomers enter into the vesicles. However this penetration is incomplete because the vesicles are in the gel state. On heating to produce the liquid crystalline state penetration of the CTAB monomers into the vesicles is facile and complete. Then on, the next and subsequent scans, the temperature at the extremum is constant. The two equilibria illustrated in Fig. 3 are therefore associated with domains that are rich in CTAB and other domains which possibly contain little CTAB. In other words the CTAB monomers cluster within several patches forming the vesicles.

With increase in [CTAB], the system initially at 15° contains CTAB micelles and DOAB vesicles. Then for example in Fig. 5, the first scan identifies two extrema corresponding to the separate micelles and vesicles. However on forming the liquid crystalline state, the penetration of the CTAB monomers and their distribution within the vesicle patches reaches an equilibrium.

In conclusion, we suggest that the complexity of the scans can be understood in terms of the difficulty of penetration of the CTAB monomers into the DOAB vesicles in the gel state relative to the liquid crystalline state. We suggest that the contrast must be borne in mind when considering surfactant-vesicle interactions.

Experimental

DOAB and CTAB were obtained as described previously^{3,7}. The DOAB aqueous solutions were prepared using the protocol previously described⁷. Thus the required amounts of DOAB(s) and water(l) were heated with stirring and held at approx. 50° for 10 min. The solution was allowed to cool and stand at room temperature for 1 h. The required amount of CTAB(s) was added with stirring at room temperature until all CTAB had dissolved.

The solution was placed in the sample cell of the calorimeter, held at 15°.

Calorimetry : The dependence on temperature of the differential isobaric heat capacities for DOAB (aq) containing known concentrations of CTAB was measured using a differential scanning micro-calorimeter (MicroCal MC-2, Amherst, MA). The reference was, in all cases, water. The scan rate was 60 Celsius per h from low to high temperatures. The data were stored on a floppy disc and analysed using the ORIGIN software as supplied by MicroCal Ltd. In all cases a water-water reference scan was recorded and subtracted from the recorded scan when DOAB solutions were placed in the sample cell. The outcome is the differential heat capacity δc_p . In the classic textbook case where the solute undergoes a transition from substance X to substance Y, the dependence of molar configurational heat capacity C_{pm} on temperature forms a bell-shaped plot with a maximum at temperature T_m ; equation(1),

$$C_{pm} = \Delta_r H^0(\text{vH}). \Delta_r H^0(\text{cal}).K/R.T^2.(1 + K)^2 \quad (1)$$

where K is the equilibrium constant at temperature T , $\Delta_r H^0(\text{vH})$ the van't Hoff enthalpy of reaction whereas $\Delta_r H^0(\text{cal})$ is the calorimetric enthalpy of reaction being obtained from the area under the 'bell' described by equation (1). In the present case, a further variable is the patch number n which describes the number of monomer units undergoing the melting transition. Hence agreement between calculated and recorded scans yields estimates of the enthalpy change, $\Delta_r H^0 [= \Delta_r H^0(\text{vH}) = \Delta_r H^0(\text{cal})]$, patch number n and melting temperature T_m

Calorimetric protocol : As commented above, DOAB solutions were placed in the sample cell held at 15°. The differential heat capacities were recorded over the range 15–90°. The solution, still held in the sample cell, was allowed to cool to 15° and then the heat capacity was rescanned from 15 to 90°. This procedure was repeated for the third time. On recooling to 15°, the solution was held at 15° for a period of 3 h before the heat capacity was rescanned. Following recooling to

15° the solution was allowed to stand at 15° for a further 3 h before rescanning. This somewhat complicate protocol was adopted because it became clear that the first scan often differed from that subsequently recorded. We were therefore anxious to confirm that we had recorded the properties of a 'limiting' equilibrium system.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank SERC for their support and the British Council for a grant to one of them (A.K.)

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